

Synthesis and Biological Activities of Certain Derivatives of 3-Aryl-4(3H)-quinazolinones. Part-II

A. DEVENDER RAO, CH. RAVI SHANKAR, P. BHAGHAVAN REDDY and V. MALLA REDDY*

University College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Kakatiya University, Warangal-506 009

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A series of 2-(*N,N*-substituted amino)methyl-3-*p*-tolyl-6,8-dibromoquinazolin-4(3*H*)-ones (4) and 2-(*N*'-acetyl-*N*'-arylsulfonamido)methyl-3-aryl-quinazolin-4(3*H*)-ones (6) have been synthesised and screened for their antifungal activity. Some of the compounds have been found to be effective antifungal agents.

QUINAZOLINONE derivatives are gaining prominence through their varied biological and pharmacological properties¹⁻⁹. In continuation of our work on various quinazolinone derivatives¹⁰ we now report the synthesis and antifungal activity of some new 2-(*N,N*-substituted amino)methyl-3-*p*-tolyl-6,8-dibromo-, and 2-(*N*'-acetyl-*N*'-aryl sulphonamido)methyl-3-aryl-6,8-substituted quinazolin-4(3*H*)-ones.

The 2-chloromethyl-3-aryl-6,8-substituted quinazolin-4(3*H*)-ones (3) have been prepared by the condensation of the respective 3,5-substituted *N*-chloroacetyl anthranilic acid₁ (1) with appropriate

aromatic amines (2) in presence of phosphorous trichloride. Compounds 3 have been characterised by their analytical, and ir spectral data ($\nu_{\max}$ 1690 (C=O), 1630 (C=N) and 1580 cm^{-1} (aromatic C=C)). Some 2-(*N,N*-substituted amino)methyl-3-*p*-tolyl-6,8-dibromo-quinazolin-4(3*H*)-ones (4; X, X' = Br, and Ar = *p*-tolyl) have been obtained by reacting the 2-chloromethyl compounds (3) with appropriate secondary amines in presence of pyridine. Compounds 4 have been characterised by their analytical, ir, and pmr data δ (acetone- d_6) 1.9 (6H, s, N(CH₃)₂), 2.3 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 4.2 (2H, s, N-CH₂) and 7.2 to 8.1 (6H, m, Ar).

- 3 and 5; a. X, X' = Br; Ar = C₆H₄-OH₂ (*p*)
 b. X, X' = H; Ar = C₆H₄-OH₂ (*o*)
 c. X, X' = H; Ar = C₆H₄-NO₂ (*p*)
 d. X, X' = H; Ar = C₆H₄-NO₂ (*o*)
 6; R = H, 2-NO₂, 3-CH₃; 8-OCH₃
 4; X, X' = Br, Ar = C₆H₄-OH₂ (*p*)
 -NR¹R² = -N(CH₃)₂, -N(C₂H₅)₂,
 -N(C₂H₅OH)₂, piperidino, morpholino

Scheme 1

The 2-chloromethyl compounds (3) have also been converted into their corresponding 2-amino-methyl-3-aryl-6,8-substituted quinazolin-4(3H)-ones (5) (ir spectra of the compounds showed strong absorptions at 3300 and 3250 cm^{-1} , confirming the presence of amino group). The compounds were further interacted with various *para*-acetamido-aryl sulphonyl chlorides in presence of dry pyridine to get 2-(N^4 -acetyl- N^1 -aryl sulphonamido)methyl-3-aryl-6,8-substituted quinazolin-4(3H)-ones (6a-m). These compounds have been purified and characterised by their analytical, ir and pmr spectral data, compound 6d : ν_{max} 3350 (NH-Ac), 3180 (NH-SO₂), 1700

(C=O, quinazolinonyl), 1680 (C=O, acetamido), 1630 (C=N), 1170 and 1320 (-SO₂-); δ (acetone-d₆) 1.2 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 2.0 (3H, s, NHCO-CH₃), 4.80 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 6.5 (1H, b, NH-SO₂-), 6.7 (1H, b, NH-Ac) and 7.6 to 8.2 (11H, m, Ar).

Antifungal activity : The compounds of type 4 and 6 were screened for their antifungal activity by standard method¹¹ at different concentrations, viz. 300, 600, 800 and 1000 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and the results are presented in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. The fungi employed in the present investigation were *Curvularia lunata* and *Fusarium oxysporum*.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL, ANALYTICAL AND ANTIFUNGAL DATA OF 3-*p*-TOLYL-2-(N,N -SUBSTITUTED AMINO)-METHYL-6,8-DIBROMO-4(3H)-QUINAZOLINONES* (4; X, X' = Br and Ar = *p*-Tolyl)

Compd. no.	R ₁ - N - R ₂	Molecular formula	M.p. °C	N% : Found/ (Calcd.)	Fungitoxicity (% inhibition**)	
					<i>C. lunata</i>	<i>F. oxysporum</i>
4a	Dimethylamino	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₂ OBr ₂	134	9.28 (9.31)	77.0, 91.3	81.0, 98.9
4b	Diethylamino	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₂ OBr ₂	120	8.72 (8.76)	22.1, 44.7	77.7, 89.8
4c	Bis(β -hydroxyethyl)amino	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ Br ₂	121	8.31 (8.34)	19.5, 40.3	67.8, 98.0
4d	Piperidino	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₂ OBr ₂	107	8.48 (8.51)	60.0, 80.1	86.2, 91.8
4e	Morpholino	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ Br ₂	122	8.46 (8.51)	60.0, 88.9	85.1, 91.7

* 65-87% yields.

** The two values are at concentration of 800 and 1000 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, respectively.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL, ANALYTICAL AND ANTIFUNGAL DATA OF 3-ARYL-2-(N^4 -ACETYL- N^1 -ARYLSULFONAMIDO)-METHYL-4(3H)-QUINAZOLINONES* (6; X, X' = Br for 6a and H for 6b-m)

Compd. no.	Ar†	R	Molecular formula	M.p. °C	N% : Found/ (Calcd.)	Fungitoxicity (% inhibition**)	
						<i>C. lunata</i>	<i>F. oxysporum</i>
6a	<i>p</i> -T	H	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ SBr ₂	182	9.00 (9.02)	22.1, 57.6	70.6, 79.0
6b	<i>p</i> -N	H	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	160	15.15 (14.19)	59.6, 100	61.0, 100
6c	<i>p</i> -N	2-NO ₂	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	115	15.58 (15.61)	100, 100	80.1, 100
6d	<i>p</i> -N	3-Me	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	185	13.75 (13.80)	47.5, 70.1	74.6, 98.4
6e	<i>p</i> -N	3-OMe	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₂ S	122	13.35 (13.38)	44.0, 66.3	75.0, 98.2
6f	<i>o</i> -T	3-OMe	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	185	11.85 (11.88)	36.4, 68.8	89.5, 100
6g	<i>o</i> -T	2-NO ₂	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	115	13.78 (13.80)	96.1, 100	75.0, 97.8
6h	<i>o</i> -T	H	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	155	12.09 (12.14)	62.1, 100	67.8, 100
6i	<i>o</i> -T	3-Me	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₂ S	180	11.70 (11.76)	51.0, 75.2	78.0, 98.8
6j	<i>o</i> -N	H	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	175	14.16 (14.19)	59.0, 100	62.8, 100
6k	<i>o</i> -N	2-NO ₂	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	120	15.60 (15.61)	98.0, 100	82.1, 100
6l	<i>o</i> -N	3-Me	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	140	13.78 (13.80)	51.6, 78.6	75.8, 96.1
6m	<i>o</i> -N	3-OMe	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₂ S	185	13.36 (13.38)	48.8, 76.3	81.2, 100

* 71-93% yield.

** The two values are at concentration of 800 and 1000 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, respectively.

† T = Toly, N = Nitrophenyl.

Experimental

The purity of the compounds has been checked by tlc. Melting points were determined in Toshniwal melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. The ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer infra-cord-283 spectrophotometer in nujol mull. Pmr spectra were recorded on a Varian EM-360 60MHz spectrophotometer using TMS as the internal reference. The physical and analytical data of compounds 4 and 6 are presented in Tables 1 and 2, respectively.

3,5-Dibromo-anthranilic acid was prepared by the method of Wheeler and Oats¹².

The *para*-acetamido arylsulphonyl chlorides required were prepared by adopting the standard procedure¹³.

2-Chloromethyl-3-aryl-6,8-substituted quinazolin-4(3H)-one (3a-d): A mixture of 3,5-substituted *N*-chloroacetyl anthranilic acid (1; 0.1 mol) arylamine (2; 0.1 mol) and phosphorous trichloride (0.1 mol) in toluene (75 ml) was refluxed under anhydrous conditions using calcium chloride guard tube for 3 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and the phosphorus trichloride was decomposed by triturating with cold water. Then, toluene was distilled off to get the product. It was filtered, washed first with a small portions of sodium bicarbonate solution (10%), then extensively with cold water, and was recrystallised from ethanol.

2-Aminomethyl-3-aryl-6,8-substituted quinazolin-4(3H)-one (5a-b): A mixture of 2-chloromethyl-3-aryl-6,8-substituted quinazolin-4(3H)-one (3; 0.2 mol) and ammonia (0.8 mol) in pyridine (30 ml) was heated gently under reflux for 3 h. Pyridine was distilled off from the reaction mixture and the residue was poured onto a little crushed ice. The product thus resulted was filtered, washed repeatedly with cold water and recrystallised from ethanol.

2-(*N,N*-Substituted amino)methyl-3-*p*-tolyl-6,8-dibromo-quinazolin-4(3H)-one (4a-e): A mixture of 2-chloromethyl-3-*p*-tolyl-6,8-dibromo-quinazolin-4(3H)-one (3, Ar=*p*-tolyl; 0.01 mol) and appropriate secondary amine (0.01 mol) in pyridine (20 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. Pyridine was distilled off as far as possible and the residue was poured onto a little crushed ice containing few drops of hydrochloric acid with stirring. It was kept aside for a few minutes and the product resulted was filtered washed with small portions of cold water, and recrystallised from ethanol.

2-(*N*⁴-Acetyl-*N*¹-aryl sulphonamido)methyl-3-aryl-6,8-substituted quinazolin-4(3H)-one (6a-m): A mixture of 2-aminomethyl-3-aryl-6,8-substituted quinazolin-4(3H)-one (5; 0.01 mol) and appropriate *p*-acetamido arylsulphonyl chloride (0.01 mol) in pyridine (25 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. Pyridine was distilled off under reduced pressure and the residue was poured onto a little crushed ice with constant stirring. It was kept aside for a few minutes, and the product resulted was filtered, was washed

thoroughly with small portions of cold water and recrystallised from ethanol.

Results and Discussion

The analytical, ir and pmr spectral data of the compounds satisfy their structural features. Compounds of type 6 were quite resistant to hydrolysis as all the attempts to deacetylate them were futile.

Among five compounds of series 4 (Table 1), compound 4a followed by compound 4d and 4e were most active against both the fungi employed. On the other hand, compounds 4b and 4c were selective in their action. *C. lunata* was comparatively more resistant towards these compounds and it could not be inhibited even to 50% at highest concentration tried. The relative higher activity of compound 4a may be due to dimethylamino moiety, whereas the fungicidal activity of compounds 4d and 4e may be attributed to the presence of piperidino and morpholino moieties, respectively.

Among thirteen compounds of series 6 (Table 2), compound 6c followed by 6g and 6k were most active which caused 50% germination inhibition at 800 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentration. Compounds 6b, 6h and 6j were found next in their fungicidal activity. Compound 6a was found to be ineffective against the fungi under investigation. Compounds 6e, 6g and 6m were selective in their action as they could inhibit the germination of only *F. oxysporum*.

From these findings one can arrive at the following conclusions:

(i) Amongst 3-substituents in compounds of series 6, *para*-nitrophenyl group was effective in checking fungal growth. *o*-tolyl and *o*-nitrophenyl groups were moderate in their fungicidal effect.

(ii) Amongst the substituents (R) in sulphonamide moiety at 2-position, the nitro-substituent was shown to be more effective than the methyl- and methoxy-substituents.

From the critical comparison of fungicidal activity of compounds of series 4 and 6, it is clear that the compounds of series 6 are more active as fungicide.

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